

**DIFFICULTIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AMONG
BACHELOR OF ARTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE STUDIES
STUDENTS AT MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU**

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Difficulties in Learning English Language Among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies Students at Mindanao State University-Sulu

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Abstract

This descriptive-exploratory study aims to determine the extent of difficulties English language studies majors at Mindanao State University-Sulu encountered during their language learning experience in the 2023–2024 academic year. employing Pearson's r correlation test, the weighted mean, the standard deviation, the t-test for independent samples, and one-way ANOVA. The study's findings are as follows: 1) Of the 100 respondents, the majority are female, in their first or second year of college, and fall between the ages of 20 and older. 2) Students at MSU-Sulu who answered the topic about how hard it is to learn English in the context of grammar and pronunciation both gave the response "Moderate." This shows that although the participants in this study, the students/respondents, may not consider these challenges as major obstacles to their ability to communicate successfully, they do encounter a moderate and balanced level of difficulty when it comes to utilizing proper grammar and pronouncing words correctly. 3) When age and gender-based groups of data are applied, the degree of difficulty BAELS students at MSU-Sulu are having learning the English language is almost always the same, with the exception of year level. However, there is a discernible difference in the level of difficulties BAELS students at MSU-Sulu encounter when studying English language when statistics are sorted by year level. This suggests that although the respondents may be of different ages and genders, their opinions of the subcategories that are included when they are categorized according to year level differ, even though they are students. 4) There is usually a significant relationship between the subcategories that make up the overall category of English learning difficulties. This strong association implies that people who struggle with accurate word pronunciation can also struggle with reading written words, which could impair their overall reading comprehension. In a similar vein, those who struggle with grammar may also have difficulties comprehending the structure and meaning of sentences, which could make it harder for them to comprehend written texts correctly.

Keywords: *difficulties, learning english, lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar*

Introduction

For students nowadays, learning foreign languages like English is a need. These days, there is a great demand for and interest in studying foreign languages, especially English, from kindergarten-age children to adult professionals. This is obviously a good thing, as learning a language is a great way to familiarize yourself with the customs and cultures of the English-speaking countries. Teaching a foreign language carries a lot of responsibilities. Teachers need to be simultaneously composed and knowledgeable. This is because learning the English language presents a number of obstacles and hurdles that children naturally face.

University graduates are expected to meet certain academic requirements, including proficiency in English and other languages. Learning a foreign language other than one's mother tongue is considered a sign of academic achievement. People from non-English speaking nations as well as those from English-speaking nations use and learn English as an international language.

The pronunciation of English, which is not native to Indonesia, is different from that of Indonesian. It is difficult for many Basic English learners to pick up the language because of these variances. In the rapidly evolving world of today, English is recognized as one of the key languages for communication and the main language of teaching. The Indonesian Ministry of Education has stressed the importance of English language competence and the need for students to show competency in the language starting in elementary school in accordance with this acknowledgment. To accomplish this and ensure that every school performs well in the subject, the Ministry of Education has established the GPMP (Gred Purata Mata Pelajaran/Subject Grade Point Average) target for English to schools in all states. A tiny percentage of schools are still unable to reach the English GPMP target because of their students' poor performance in the subject.

English language instruction is offered in both public and private institutions in the Philippines. Despite unchecked globalization, the country continues to offer top-notch education to both domestic and international pupils. The government started luring international students to the Philippines in the 1980s, mostly for studies in agriculture and medical. Ten years later, a large number of educational establishments provided short-term courses in aviation, maritime studies, hotel and restaurant management, and English language.

The Philippines has been a significant Asian hub for education, and since then, getting a visa has become easier for overseas students. Furthermore, the Philippine government established exchange programs for local institutions to engage in with foreign colleges, specifically those in Australia, the US, Korea, Canada, and Europe (Tempo, 2012).

Due to the previously mentioned factors, there has been an increase in the quantity of foreign students enrolling in postsecondary institutions in the Philippines. For instance, from 2,323 in 2001 to 5,136 in 2006, there was a sharp 48 percent decline to barely 2,665

in 2008 (Tayag, 2013). Despite the notable decline, the number of international students enrolled in Philippine higher education institutions rose to 7,776 in 2011 (CHED, online). The Philippines is rapidly emerging as a major hub for education in the Asia-Pacific region, as seen by the growing number of foreign students studying there, according to the Philippine Bureau of Immigration. The growing number of international students choosing to study in the Philippines is evidence of the rising caliber and standard of instruction offered by the nation's educational institutions (Aning, 2011).

Nevertheless, widespread usage of the Filipino language across the country is unavoidable. Aside from the fact that Filipino is the national language of the Philippines as specified by Sections 6–9, Article XIV of the Philippine Constitution, code-switching between Filipino and English has been relevant in academic settings. The growing acceptance of code-switching remains a controversial subject among academics. Bernardo (2005), however, asserts that it can be a "legitimate and potent resource for learning and teaching for bilingual students and teachers," and that instead of strictly enforcing the language prescription in formal classes, Filipinos should relax it to the benefit of both students and teachers.

Due to the widespread use of Filipino in the Philippines, international students are now having difficulty participating in class discussions when the language is being taught in Filipino. These days, learning a second language is crucial for international students. According to Cook (1996), being able to communicate in another language can lead to a variety of opportunities, such as the ability to work, pursue an education, and participate more fully in one's own life when there is a chance to immigrate abroad. It can also broaden one's literary and cultural horizons and allow one to express their political or religious beliefs.

The Tausug students in the Sulu Archipelago, especially those at Mindanao State University-Sulu, face challenges when it comes to learning English. According to my many years of teaching experience, the majority of students, particularly those in their first year, lack a solid foundation in English and have limited vocabulary. As a result, they often find it difficult to communicate in the classroom and, naturally, to pay attention to the teacher when they use English during class discussions.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to ascertain the challenges faced by language learners, particularly those enrolled in Mindanao State University-Sulu's Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies program. The 100 Bachelor of Arts in English Language (BAELS) students from Mindanao State University-Sulu were the study's participants. This study examined the challenges that prevented individuals from doing well in the subject by using a questionnaire as the instrument. The study's conclusions and discussion will be useful in assisting parents, teachers, and school administrators in making decisions that will increase the English language proficiency of their students.

Research Questions

This study assessed the level of challenges that Mindanao State University (MSU) in Sulu's Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students faced when learning the language in the academic year 2023–2024. It provided specific answers to the following queries:

1. What is the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender; and
 - 1.3. year level?
2. What is the extent of difficulties in learning English Language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of:
 - 2.1. pronunciation; and
 - 2.2. grammar?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of difficulties in learning English Language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University-Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of:
 - 3.1. age;
 - 3.2. gender; and
 - 3.3. year level?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under extent of difficulties in learning English Language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University-Sulu?

Literature Review

Every research project needs to be aware of the historical context in order to achieve its goals and justify its findings. Numerous studies on the subject of challenges encountered when learning English have been conducted.

Foreign Literature and Studies

The "Challenges Faced by Newari Students in Learning English" study was carried out by Shrestha (2015) in an effort to ascertain the challenges that Newari 14 students face in their language learning endeavors. A mixed method research methodology was used in this

study. Forty-five Newari secondary school pupils from the Kathmandu Valley were selected as a sample using purposeful non-random sampling. He used questionnaires and semi-structured interviews as research tools. Data analysis and interpretations of the findings revealed that Newari students had trouble picking up vocabulary, spelling, grammar, and pronunciation during their English language lessons.

According to Neupane (2016), the purpose of the study "Questioning Structures in Magar Dhut and English" was to identify the questioning structures used in Magar Dhut and to compare and contrast them with the English language. He selected sixty native Magar Dhut speakers from Krishna Gandaki VDC and Jagatra Devi VDC as informants for the study by using a deliberate non-random sampling technique. The research tool used was a set of questionnaires. He found that there are five distinct types of questions in the Magar Dhut language, and that there are distinct open interrogative question indicators in both Magar Dhut and English.

The main objective of Chaudhary's (2019) study, "Problems and Challenges Faced by Tharu Students in Learning English," was to investigate the perceptions of Tharu students regarding the English language. The researcher collected data from four secondary community schools in Gadhawa Dang. Respondents were selected via non-random purposive sampling. The data collection instruments included both closed-ended and open-ended questions. Her main findings were that the learners' low comprehension level is a result of their social status and culture. Their vocabulary is insufficient, and they have poor pronunciation, intonation, and tone. Additionally, their grasp of language is really poor.

Research on "Students Difficulties in Learning English Speaking Skill at SMA N5 Jambi" was conducted by Tiara Tama Ardila (2017). The goal of this study was to determine the challenges faced by students as they learned to speak English. The findings indicated that students' confidence issues stem from their fear of making mistakes when speaking English. Speaking in English also made them uneasy and anxious. When it comes to vocabulary and pronunciation, they struggle to finish the sentences. They acknowledge their want to talk fluently. According to this study, students should work through their personal English language learning challenges. They can read English-language books and articles to help them with their vocabulary.

Ulfa Yusica (2015) conducted a study titled "Problem Faced by Thai Student in Speaking English," which aims to identify the issues that Thai students face and to explain why the majority of students in Thailand struggle with speaking the language. Language proficiency is one of the four English language skills that may be the most challenging for students to master. A number of factors contribute to Thai students' difficulty speaking the language, particularly when it comes to oral communication. These include age or maturational constraints, audio media, socio-cultural factors, Thailand's history of never having been colonized by a European nation, and effective factors. The psychological component of Thai students' attitudes remains heavily influenced by the effective variables, which include shyness, lack of confidence, anxiety, self-doubt, frustration, unease, and motivation. Furthermore, a major factor influencing the effectiveness of teaching English in a classroom could be the teacher. The teacher-center method is still being used by non-native educators, who prioritize teaching grammar above speaking skills.

According to Charisse M. Tocmo, proficiency is the capacity to apply skills and knowledge to reach a level of competence. It could be advantageous for someone's cover letter or resume. To be skilled in a given field is to be an expert in it. English is one of the most widely spoken languages, especially in the Philippines. Actually, it is the world tongue. Proficiency in English language usage and composition can lead to opportunities and success. Some people buy and read English-language books, newspapers, and other texts to improve their language skills. Therefore, we need to become fluent in English in the workplace, in the classroom, and in interpersonal interactions if we want to stay competitive in the global economy.

Since many Filipino exam takers were anticipated to be "educated," Andrew King, the country director of IDP Education for the Philippines, said that the overall average result was unacceptable. Mr. King, who has resided in the Philippines for over 12 years, claims that the country, which takes pride in its linguistic abilities, is seeing a decline in English competence. The standard of English spoken by teachers is deteriorating, and there is now only one English television station instead of four. Even English textbooks contain a lot of mistakes. "This is a significant issue, particularly for a nation attempting to draw in call center business," stated US businessman Russ Sandlin, who recently closed his call center in Manila due to a shortage of English-speaking staff.

In their research, Wyk et al. (2016) observed that despite widespread objections and continuous justifications for using MT as the primary language of instruction in the early years of schooling, a variety of factors have persuaded people to reject this idea and choose to use the dominant language, or the Language of Wider Communication (such as English), in schools as soon as feasible. The "maximum exposure hypothesis" (also known as the "time-on-task hypothesis"), which postulates that an individual's performance in a language would increase with experience, is explained by Wyk et al. (2016). She also insisted that since pupils will be able to accomplish homework in English earlier and more successfully, they should receive more direct teaching in the language.

Furthermore, Wyk et al. (2016) assert that improved academic achievement depends greatly on having a solid foundation in the English language. They also recommended that the length of the English study and teaching terms be expanded. Many teachers, students, and parents of students attending provincial schools are unable to fully understand the MTB-MLE because they believe it will negatively and cripplingly affect their children's ability to develop their English language skills. Some educators believe that English and Filipino are already used as the official languages of higher education. Increased linguistic confusion on the part of students who must switch up their language attitudes across the various classes they enroll in at school can result from adding additional languages to the medium

of teaching, such as their mother tongue. Since most regional mother tongues are barely "intellectualized languages," many educators have also questioned how the students' mother tongue can be promoted as a medium of instruction for specific academic disciplines. The intellectualization of Filipino, the country's official language, is already questioned; this is especially true of the regional languages spoken there, which were hardly ever utilized to convey or express scientific information. It has also been disputed that mastering the language in one's mother tongue can serve as a necessary precursor to learning English as a second language. Numerous regional languages spoken in the Philippines require syntactic, lexical, orthographic, and phonemic elements that are very different from those found in the English language system. As a result, learners are unable to identify as many similarities between the grammar rules of their native languages and the English language. As a result, learners are unable to identify as many similarities between the grammar rules of their native languages and the English language. Given the aforementioned circumstances, the researcher hypothesizes that the majority of these opinions may be influenced by teachers' lack of familiarity with the best advantages of using mother tongue-based instruction, as evidenced by observations he has made of his fellow educators and articles he has read that highlight the persistent criticisms of the MTB-MLE. In light of this, the purpose of this study was to uncover the professional attitudes and underlying beliefs of instructors as they relate to the MTB-MLE. This study aimed to give empirical support for either side of the debate on the potential impact of mother tongue-based instruction on the English language proficiency of students pursuing both English and mother tongue courses concurrently. Additionally, the study examined students' English language proficiency and challenges, which falls under the researcher's area of expertise.

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive exploratory research design using a quantitative research method was used to determine the degree of difficulties in learning English language among Mindanao State University-Sulu Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students in order to realize the comprehensive layout for the data collection in this study.

Respondents

The one hundred (100) students who completed their Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies at Mindanao State University-Sulu in the academic year 2023–2024 served as the study's respondents. The respondents in this study were specifically Mindanao State University-Sulu students enrolled in the English program within the College of Arts and Sciences (CAS) department. For each Year Level, representative samples of students were chosen at random. The study's sample distribution is displayed in the table below.

Distribution of samples according to Year Level	
<i>Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies</i>	<i>Number of BAELS Student-Respondents</i>
First Year College	32
Second Year College	30
Third Year College	23
Fourth Year College	15
Total	100

Instruments

The study's instrument is a template from Kanwal Shahzadi's earlier investigation, "Difficulties face in learning English language skills by University of Sargodha's Students." The age, gender, and year level profiles of the pupils are covered in the first section of the questionnaire. In the second section of the survey, the degree of difficulty with learning English is assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 representing extremely high, 4 representing high, 3 representing moderate, 2 representing low, and 1 representing extremely low.

Procedure

In order to gather data, permission to distribute the questionnaire was requested from Sulu State College's Deady Studies, Mindanao State University's Chancellor, and the College of Arts and Sciences Dean. The launch, administration, and retrieval of the questionnaire were all carried out by the researcher in person. Following that, the questionnaire was completed, and the data were presented, analyzed, and interpreted. After then, the completed document was turned in for editing and finalization.

Results and Discussion

The results based on the data collected for this study are presented, analyzed, and explained in this chapter. It also illustrates the degree of English language learning challenges faced by Mindanao State University-Sulu students pursuing a bachelor's degree in English language studies. Along with the degree of difficulties in learning English, it also shows the respondents' demographic profiles in terms of age, gender, and year level. When data are categorized based on respondents' demographic profiles, there is a significant correlation and difference in these sub-categories.

The presentations, analyses, and interpretations of the findings that follow are based on how the data collected for this study was

properly scored and statistically treated in order to address each of the research questions:

1. What is the Demographic Profile of the students-respondents in terms of: 1.1 Age, 1.2 Gender; and 1.3 Year Level?

1.1 In terms of Age

The age-based demographic profile of respondents who were college students is displayed in Table 1.1. This table shows that, of the 100 students who responded, 0 (0.0%) were under the age of 17, 22 (22.0%) were between the ages of 18 and 19, and 78 (78.0%) were 20 years of age and older. This survey shows that over half of all the respondents, who are students, are in the age range of 20 years old and older. This further suggests that the majority of the respondents in this study, who are students, are classified as belonging to the upper age group.

Table 1.1. Demographic profile of BAELS students-respondents of Mindanao State University in terms of age

Age	Number of students	Percent
17 years old and below	0	0.0%
18-19 years old	22	22.0%
20 years old and above	78	78.0%
Total	100	100%

1.2 In terms of Gender

The gender demographic profile of respondents who were college students is displayed in Table 1.2. This table indicates that, of the 100 students who responded, 18 (18.0%) are men and 82 (82.0%) are women. This survey indicates that female college students make up the majority of the overall number of participants, or responses. This suggests even more that women make up the vast majority of Mindanao State University respondents.

Table 1.2. Demographic profile of BAELS students-respondents of Mindanao State University in terms of gender

Gender	Number of students	Percent
Male	18	18.0%
Female	82	82.0%
Total	100	100%

1.3 In terms of Year Level

The year-level demographic profile of respondents who were college students is displayed in Table 1.3. This table shows that, of the 100 students who responded, 32 (32.0%) are in their first year, 30 (30.0%) are in their second year, 25 (25.0%) are in their third year, and 10 (10.0%) are in their fourth year. This suggests that first- and second-year students make up more than half of the overall number of respondents in this study.

Table 1.3. Demographic profile of BAELS students-respondents of Mindanao State University in terms of year level

Year Level	Number of students	Percent
First Year level	32	32.0%
Second Year level	30	30.0%
Third Year level	23	23.0%
Fourth Year level	15	15.0%
Total	100	100%

2. What is the extent of difficulties in learning English Language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of: 2.1 Pronunciation and 2.2 Grammar?

2.1 In the context of Pronunciation

Table 2.1. Extent of college students' difficulties in learning English language at Mindanao State University-Sulu in the context of Pronunciation

	Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1	Fluent English Pronunciation is difficult for me.	3.49	1.087	Moderate
2	I am afraid that other students will laugh at me because of my pronunciation.	3.51	1.078	High
3	I don't want to participate in the class when the teachers ask to read.	3.00	1.189	Moderate
4	I feel nervous when teachers make an oral examination.	3.43	1.027	Moderate
5	I mispronounce certain sounds in English.	3.46	.947	Moderate
6	Lack of knowledge contributes to pronunciation errors.	3.26	.960	Moderate
7	Students have major problems with phonetic transcription.	3.43	.946	Moderate
8	Students make pronunciation errors because of lack of practice rules.	3.48	1.049	Moderate
9	Mother-tongue interference leads to pronunciation errors.	3.32	1.072	Moderate
10	lack of confidence in pronouncing words correctly.	3.73	.973	High
	Total Weighted Mean	3.411	0.57452	Moderate

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Extremely High; (4) 3.50-4.49=High; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Moderate; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Low; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Extremely Low

The degree of difficulty college students at Mindanao State University-Sulu have studying the English language in the context of pronunciation is displayed in Table 2.1. This category is classified as "Moderate" after receiving a weighted mean score of 3.411 overall with a standard deviation of 0.57452. This finding suggests that the college students who took part in the research acknowledged that they have mild pronunciation difficulties. This suggests that the respondents, who are students, have faced reasonable challenges related to their language proficiency.

The following items were notably rated as "Moderate" by students who responded to the survey: "I find it difficult to pronounce fluent English sounds," "I feel anxious when teachers give an oral exam," "I mispronounce certain sounds in English," "I lack knowledge that contributes to pronunciation errors," "Students have significant issues with phonetic transcription," and "Pronunciation errors are caused by mother-tongue interference."

2.2 In the context of Grammar

The degree to which Mindanao State University-Sulu college students struggle with learning the English language in the context of grammar is displayed in Table 2.2. This category is classified as "Moderate" after receiving a weighted mean score of 3.483 overall with a standard deviation of 0.63865. This finding suggests that the college students who took part in the research acknowledged that they have a modest amount of difficulty preserving grammatical precision. Moreover, this suggests that although the students who responded may have a fair understanding of the principles of grammar, they may occasionally struggle to apply them correctly.

Notably, students who responded to the survey rated the following items as "Moderate": "I feel less confident in my learning of basic grammar rules." "Correct grammar confuses me when I speak." "I find grammar lesson in textbook is quite challenging and difficult for me." and "I feel less motivated to learn more about grammar to improve my language proficiency."

Table 2.2. Extent of BAELS students-respondents' difficulties in learning English language at Mindanao State University-Sulu in the context of Motivation

	Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1	Due to poor grammar, students are not able to learn English as second Language.	3.42	1.174	Moderate
2	Correct grammar confuses me when I speak.	3.40	.943	Moderate
3	I find it challenging to remember and apply complex grammar rules.	3.90	.959	High
4	I am afraid of grammatical errors.	3.51	1.096	High
5	I often make grammar mistakes when speaking and writing.	3.63	.906	High
6	I feel afraid of being center of attention because of my grammar.	3.59	.922	High
7	I find grammar lesson in textbook is quite challenging and difficult for me.	3.27	.827	Moderate
8	I feel less confident in my learning of basic grammar rules.	3.40	1.005	Moderate
9	I feel less motivation to learn more about grammar to improve my language proficiency.	3.35	1.149	Moderate
10	I can't easily identify the correct grammar in my own writing.	3.51	1.040	High
Total Weighted Mean		3.483	0.63865	Moderate

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Extremely High; (4) 3.50-4.49=High; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Moderate; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Low; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Extremely Low

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of difficulties in learning English Language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University-Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of: 3.1 Age, 3.2 Gender, and 3.3 Year Level?

3.1 According to Age

When data are grouped based on the age distribution of the BAELS students at MSU-Sulu, Table 3.1 illustrates the variation in the degree of difficulty in learning English language. The t-values and probability values are in fact significant at alpha 0.05, as this table illustrates. This indicates that even if the respondents are students, their perceptions of the degree of difficulty in learning English language are largely the same. This further suggests that respondents who are 20 years of age or older may not perceive the level of difficulty in learning English language as much as those who are between the ages of 18 and 19 years old, or vice versa.

Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that respondents who are college students at MSU-Sulu view the degree of difficulty associated with learning English language differently depending on their age. Thus, the following hypothesis is accepted: "When data are grouped according to age, there is no significant difference in the extent of difficulties in learning English language among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu."

Table 3.1. Difference in the extent of difficulties in learning English Language among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu when data are grouped according to age

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Pronunciation	18-19 years old	3.33	0.64319	-0.102	-0.730	0.467	Not Significant
	20 years old and above	3.43	0.55611				
Grammar	18-19 years old	3.42	0.61079	-0.069	-0.448	0.655	Not Significant
	20 years old and above	3.49	0.64930				

* Significant at alpha 0.05

3.2 According to Gender

The variation in the degree of challenges with learning English language among MSU-Sulu BAELS students is shown in Table 3.2, which is categorized based on the students' gender-specific demographic profile. The t-values and probability values of all the subcategories included in the degree of difficulty learning English language are not significant at alpha 0.05, as this table illustrates. This indicates that there is no difference in the respondents' perceptions of the degree of difficulty associated with learning English between male and female students who participated in the study. This suggests further that the responder student's gender may not have improved his perception of the degree of difficulty associated with learning English, or vice versa.

Therefore, it is safe to conclude that variable gender has no discernible impact on respondents' perceptions on the degree of challenges BAELS students at MSU-Sulu face when studying English. As a result, the hypothesis that reads, "When data are grouped according to gender, there is no significant difference in the extent of difficulties in learning English language among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu," is accepted.

Table 3.2. *Difference in the extent of difficulties in learning English Language among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu when data are grouped according to gender*

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Pronunciation	Male	3.37	.60876	-.05406	-.360	.720	Not Significant
	Female	3.42	.57019				
Grammar	Male	3.30	.69080	-.21304	-1.286	.202	Not Significant
	Female	3.52	.62457				

* Significant at alpha 0.05

3.3 According to Year Level

When data are grouped based on the year level and the demographic profile of the BAELS students at MSU-Sulu, Table 3.3 illustrates the variation in the degree of difficulty in learning English language. This table indicates that, in contrast to "Grammar," "Pronunciation" has F-values and probability values that are significant at alpha 0.05. This indicates that even if the respondents in this study are students at different year levels, their perspectives on the "degree of difficulties in learning English Language specifically on the context of "Pronunciation"" generally differ. It suggests that, compared to students in the first, second, or third year, those in the fourth year may have a greater understanding of the degree of difficulty in learning English language in the context of pronunciation, and vice versa. As a result, the hypothesis that reads, "When data are grouped according to year level, there is no significant difference in the extent of difficulties in learning English language among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu," is rejected.

Table 3.3. *Difference in the extent of difficulties in learning English Language among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu when data are grouped according to year level*

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Pronunciation	Between Groups	3.292	3	1.097	3.585	.017*	Significant
	Within Groups	28.386	96	.306			
	Total	32.678	99				
Grammar	Between Groups	3.212	3	1.071	2.766	.056	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.168	96	.387			
	Total	40.380	99				

* Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test was conducted to identify which among groups classified according to year level have different levels of mean in the extent of difficulties in learning English Language when data are grouped according to students-respondents' demographic profile in terms of year level.

On Pronunciation: It shows that First-year students-respondents obtained a mean difference of $-.50770^*$ with a Standard Error of .17312 and a p-value of .022, which is significant at alpha 0.05 over fourth-year level students-respondents. This indicates that the first-year level does not differ in perception towards the extent of difficulties in learning English Language with second- and third-year levels however they differ with those of the fourth-year level students.

Table 3.3.1. *Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the extent of difficulties in learning English Language among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of year level*

Dependent Variable	(I)	(J)	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
	Grouping by Year Level				
	Grouping by Year Level	Grouping Year Level			
Pronunciation	First Year level	Second Year level	-.34437	.14060	.075
		Third Year level	-.28654	.15124	.237
		Fourth Year level	-.50770*	.17312	.022

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under extent of difficulties in learning English Language among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu?

The link between the subcategories covered by the degree of English language learning challenges experienced by BAELS students at MSU-Sulu is displayed in Table 4. The calculated Pearson correlation coefficients (Pearson r) between these variables are significant at alpha 0.05, as the table illustrates. Additionally, the degree of link between the severity of reading comprehension issues and BAELS students at MSU-Sulu is as follows:

1. Extremely high positive degree of association between "pronunciation" and "grammar" and the level of difficulty learning the English language.

The outcome shows a substantial correlation between these linguistic factors: the more students-respondents struggle with "pronunciation" when learning English, the more they struggle with "grammar," and vice versa. In the meantime, it can be said that there is typically a very strong correlation between the size of the subcategories included in the reading comprehension problem.

Consequently, the hypothesis that claims, "Among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu, there is no significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under extent of difficulties in learning English language" is rejected.

Table 4 shows the correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of difficulties in learning English Language among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu.

Table 4. *The correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of difficulties in learning English Language among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu*

Variables		Pearson r	Sig.	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Pronunciation	Grammar	.757*	.000	100	Very High

*Correlation coefficient is significant at alpha .05; Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002): 0.0-0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.3 = Low; 0.3-0.5 = Moderate; 0.5-0.7 = High; 0.7-0.9 = Very High; 0.9-1 = Nearly Perfect

Conclusion

The study concludes the following: A preponderance of females characterizes the demographic profile of students-respondents in the MSU-Sulu BAELS program. Furthermore, a sizable majority is in the age range of 20 years and older. Moreover, the bulk of students who responded are first- and second-year students. Program administrators and educators can use these insights regarding the student-respondent population to better customize academic and support services to the unique needs of this demographic. Students-respondents struggle with their language skills and adapt to obstacles in a moderate way.

In general, demographic characteristics like age and gender have little bearing on how respondents, or students, evaluate the degree of difficulty in learning English; nevertheless, they do have differing opinions regarding year level. Subcategories subsumed under the extent of difficulties in learning English Language have a very high positively correlation implying a strong interdependence among them.

This study recommends the following: School administrators may invest in technology tools and resources to help pupils learn proper pronunciation and grammar. This exposes students to real-world language usage, which helps them comprehend grammar rules and improve their pronunciation skills. MSU-Sulu educators may use a wide range of multimodal learning resources, including as visual aids, interactive multimedia, and hands-on activities. This accommodates a variety of learning styles while also reinforcing linguistic skills in unique ways. Educators should provide regular comments on pronunciation and grammar performance. Implement formative assessments to measure progress and highlight areas that need more attention.

Moreover, future researchers in the field of Language Education are encouraged to conduct studies like this one to contribute to ongoing research on improving linguistic skills holistically among college students and provide a foundation for continued advancements in the field.

References

- Aboagye, E., Yawson, J. A., Appiah, K. N. (2020) "The challenges of students in Tertiary Institution"
- Abrar, M. (2016) "Teaching English Problems" Educ Stud English 61,103-131, Google Scholar
- Allen, E., & Valette, R. (2015) "Classroom Technique: Foreign Languages and English as a second Languages and English as a second Language". San Diego, Harecourt Brace Jovanovich.
- Anyiendah, M. S. (2017) "Challenges Faced by Teachers When Teaching English in Public Primary Schools in Kenya"
- Brown, H. D. (2015) "Principle of Language Learning and teaching". New Jersey & NY: Mcgraw-Hill.
- Case, R. E., & Taylor, S. S. (2015) "Difference or Learning Language Answers from a linguistic perspective". ERIC Clearing House,

78(3), 127–130. <http://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ710918>.

Cogan, J., & Flecker, M. (2010) “Dyslexia in Secondary School. A Practical Handbook for Teachers, Parents & Students”. London: Whurr Publishers Ltd. Ganshow, L., & Schneider, E. (2011). At-risk students and the study of a foreign language in school. Fact Sheet 25.

Hasan, K. (2015) “A Linguistic Study of English language curriculum at the Secondary Level in Bangladesh”. A Communicative Approach to Curriculum Development. *Language in India*, 48, 1-240. Krashen, S. D. (1981). *Second Language Acquisition and Second Language Learning*. Pergamon Press Inc.

Joel Meniado (2019). “Demographic Variables and English Proficiency of Adult Language Learners”: A Correlational Study. 001.10.31014/ajor. 1993.02.01.38

Lokerson, J. (2016) “Learning Strategies”: Glossary of Some Important Terms. Education Resources Information Center. Retrieved from <http://www.eric.ed.gov>

Misbah, N.H., Mohamad, M., Yunus, M. Md., Ya’acub, A., Dua, S.K.P., and Persekutuan, W., Malaysia. Identifying the Factors Contributing to Students Difficulties in the English Language Learning. Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan, Malaysia. 001.10.42.36/cc.2017.813136

Neliti (2022) “Difficulties of learning English” at <https://media.netili.com>

Nelson. Townend, J. (2015) “Principles of Teaching” – The DI Literacy Programme. The Dyslexia Institute. Retrieved from http://www.dyslexia-inst.org.uk/articles/prin_teach.htm Wadlington, E., Jacob, S., & Bailey, S. (2011) Teaching Students with Dyslexia in the Regular Classroom. *Childhood Education*. Gale Group.1-5.

Reed, B., & Railsback, J. (2010) “Strategies and Resources for Mainstream Teachers of English Language Learners”. Portland: Northwest Regional Educational Laboratory.

Schneider, E., & Crombie, M. (2010) “Dyslexia and Foreign Language Learning”. London: David Fulton Publishers.

S. M Ariana, (2008) “Teaching English in several Central and Eastern European Countries” *International Journal of Educational Research open*, 1, 100011

Tough, J. (2010) “Young Children Learning English Languages”. Inc. Brumfit, J. Moon, & R. Tongue (Eds.), *Teaching English to Children from Practice to Principle* (pp. 213-227).

Z. A. D. A. Ahmed, (2017) “Difficulties encountered by EFL Students in learning English”: A case study of Sudanese higher secondary schools.

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